

ANDIS Clusters

Operationalisation for a Simplified Classification of Diabetes Mellitus

Classification Table

Type	Cluster	Age (years)	BMI (kg/m ²)	Beta-cell antibodies
1	SAID	< 35		positive
	LADA	≥ 35		positive
2	SIDD	< 60	< 30	negative
	SIRD	≥ 60	≥ 30	negative
	MOD	< 60	≥ 30	negative
	MARD	≥ 60	< 30	negative

SAID: severe autoimmune diabetes

LADA: latent autoimmune diabetes of adults

SIDD: severe insulin-deficient diabetes

SIRD: severe insulin-resistant diabetes

MOD: mild obesity-related diabetes

MARD: mild age-related diabetes

ANDIS: All New Diabetics in Scania

References

1. Ahlqvist E, Storm P, Käräjämäki A, Martinell M, Dorkhan M, Carlsson A, Vikman P, Prasad RB, Aly DM, Almgren P, Wessman Y, Shaat N, Spégel P, Mulder H, Lindholm E, Melander O, Hansson O, Malmqvist U, Lernmark Å, Lahti K, Forsén T, Tuomi T, Rosengren AH, Groop L. Novel subgroups of adult-onset diabetes and their association with outcomes: a data-driven cluster analysis of six variables. *Lancet Diabetes Endocrinol.* 2018 May;6(5):361-369. doi: 10.1016/S2213-8587(18)30051-2. Epub 2018 Mar 5. PMID: 29503172.
2. Ahlqvist E, Tuomi T, Groop L. Clusters provide a better holistic view of type 2 diabetes than simple clinical features. *Lancet Diabetes Endocrinol.* 2019 Sep;7(9):668-669. doi: 10.1016/S2213-8587(19)30257-8. PMID: 31439272.
3. Abu Rached N, Gambichler T, Ocker L, Dietrich JW, Quast DR, Sieger C, Seifert C, Scheel C, Bechara FG. Screening for Diabetes Mellitus in Patients with Hidradenitis Suppurativa-A Monocentric Study in Germany. *Int J Mol Sci.* 2023 Apr 1;24(7):6596. doi: 10.3390/ijms24076596. PMID: 37047569; PMCID: PMC10094965.
4. Abu Rached N, Dietrich JW, Ocker L, Stockfleth E, Haven Y, Myszkowski D, Bechara FG. Endotyping Insulin-Glucose Homeostasis in Hidradenitis Suppurativa: The Impact of Diabetes Mellitus and Inflammation. *J Clin Med.* 2025 Mar 21;14(7):2145. doi: 10.3390/jcm14072145. PMID: 40217596; PMCID: PMC11990022.